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Global Futures Bulletin

**CLIMATE-NATURE
SYNERGIES
AT COP30
AND BEYOND**

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CLIMATE–NATURE SYNERGIES AT COP30 AND BEYOND¹

Introduction

COP30 in Belém in 2025 marked a substantive step forward in advancing climate-nature synergies within the United Nations (UN) climate process. For the first time, linkages between climate action, ecosystem protection, and land governance were reflected across all four pillars of a UN Climate Change Conference (COP): the Leaders Summit, negotiated outcomes, the Action Agenda, and broader societal mobilization in Belém and beyond.²

While institutional fragmentation across the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and the United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (UNCCD) – together known as the Rio Conventions – persists, COP30 delivered concrete political and procedural developments that help create the basis for more integrated implementation in the years ahead.

Why Belém Mattered for Climate-Nature Synergies

COP30 convened at a moment of escalating planetary crisis and renewed political momentum around climate-nature synergies. More than thirty years after the 1992 Rio Earth Summit, the UN climate process returned to Brazil, this time for the first Climate COP ever held in the Amazon. Although the three Rio Conventions were established together, they have largely evolved in silos, with limited coordination and few mechanisms to support integrated implementation.

In recent years, climate-nature synergies have regained political prominence, driven by intensifying climate impacts, accelerating biodiversity loss and land degradation, and growing recognition of the costs of fragmented governance. Yet the continued absence of institutional mechanisms for global policy coherence across the climate, biodiversity, and land agendas constrains systemic action, leading to duplicative efforts, fragmented financing and weak alignment in support of national implementation.³

In 2024, both the CBD and UNCCD at their respective COP16 meetings adopted concrete measures to strengthen policy coherence and multilateral coordination (CBD COP Decision 16/22 and UNCCD COP Decision 8/COP.16).⁴

This contrasted with the UNFCCC, where no substantive progress on climate-nature synergies was achieved that year, despite the first Global Stocktake adopted at COP28 having clearly affirmed that meeting the Paris Agreement goals requires addressing land-use change and ecosystem loss alongside energy transitions, including halting and reversing deforestation by 2030 and mobilizing finance for forest conservation and sustainable management (paragraphs 33 and 34).⁵

Against this backdrop, COP30 in Belém brought climate-nature synergies closer to the core of the climate process. Convening in the Amazon – the world’s largest tropical forest and one of its most significant carbon and biodiversity reservoirs – the Conference underscored the urgency of linking climate action, ecosystem protection and sustainable development within a more integrated implementation agenda.

Building on this momentum, COP30 moved nature closer to the center of the climate agenda and elevated climate-nature synergies as a shared political priority across governments, multilateral institutions and non-state actors. This Bulletin examines the outcomes from Belém across the four pillars of COP30 – the Leaders Summit, negotiations, the Action Agenda and mobilization – and assesses how these developments shape pathways toward more integrated governance and implementation in the lead-up to UNFCCC COP31, UNCCD COP17, and CBD COP17 in 2026.

By bringing these strands together, the Bulletin explores what COP30 delivered for the Climate-Nature Synergies Agenda, where and how political momentum is consolidating, and the remaining gaps between ambition and negotiated outcomes. It also provides a forward-looking basis for more coherent, high-impact implementation across the Rio Conventions as the system moves toward an aligned COP cycle in 2026.

1. Leaders Summit: Elevating Political Momentum

The Climate–Nature Synergies Agenda calls for cooperation across the Rio Conventions to move beyond legal and political dialogue and translate into practical mechanisms for implementation. In this context, initiatives such as the Tropical Forests Forever Facility (TFFF),⁶ along with commitments to strengthen efforts to combat environmental crime and promote nature-based solutions and the bioeconomy, illustrate the type of cross-cutting action needed to operationalize synergies.⁷ By addressing the structural drivers of deforestation and degradation and providing predictable long-term finance for conservation and sustainable development, these initiatives create enabling conditions for integrated delivery across climate, biodiversity, and land agendas.

The Leaders Summit on 6 and 7 of November 2025 provided clear political signals on the need to advance climate-nature integration. In his address, Brazil’s President Lula called⁸ for coordinated global roadmaps to phase out fossil fuels, halt and reverse deforestation, and mobilize the resources needed to deliver these transitions. Among these, the proposed global roadmap to end deforestation emerged as a concrete expression of climate-nature synergies, bringing together emissions reduction, ecosystem protection, and territorial governance within a single implementation pathway.

President Lula further stressed that delivering such integrated roadmaps would require stronger global governance arrangements, including his proposal for a Climate Council linked to the United Nations General Assembly.⁹

In this sense, additional initiatives announced at the Summit further reinforced the climate-nature nexus. Brazil formally launched the TFFF at the Leaders Summit, alongside heads of state and government from tropical forest countries and partner governments, signaling high-level political endorsement for a new global financing instrument for forests. The launch was accompanied by a joint declaration initially endorsed by 53 countries, as well as announcements of more than USD 5.5 billion in initial commitments.¹⁰ The TFFF aims to mobilize long-term, predictable finance for forest conservation and sustainable territorial development, positioning forests as a strategic pillar of climate action. Further operational aspects of the Facility are addressed in the Action Agenda section.

Furthermore, a dedicated high-level session on Climate and Nature: Forests and Oceans during the Leaders Summit resulted in the endorsement of the *Call to Action on Integrated Fire Management and Wildfire Resilience*.¹¹ The Call reaffirmed commitments to halt and reverse deforestation and forest degradation by 2030, in line with the first Global Stocktake, recognized the growing wildfire risks driven by climate change and land degradation and their transboundary impacts, and underscored the need to strengthen coordinated efforts to prevent, monitor, and combat illegal forest fires as part of broader action to tackle environmental crime.

2. Negotiations: Procedural Advances with Strategic Implications

Unlike the CBD, the UNFCCC does not have a dedicated agenda item to discuss climate-nature integration. With no political mandate to create new items at COP30, aligned with Brazil's Presidency's focus on implementation,¹² Parties and observers seeking to advance synergies identified the item *Cooperation with Other International Organizations*, nested within the Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice (SBSTA), as a viable entry point.

At SB62 in Bonn, in June 2025, after significant political mobilization, Parties agreed to incorporate the issue of synergies into this existing item and to discuss it on an exceptional basis at the November session, creating a procedural foothold to advance a potential substantial decision on synergies at COP30.¹³ In Belém, three technical meetings and three Presidency consultations advanced the debate, with clear “champions” – including Colombia, Brazil, the European Union (EU), the Environmental Integrity Group (EIG), the United Kingdom (UK), Canada, Panama and several African and Small Island Developing States (SIDS) such as Gambia, Zimbabwe, Nigeria, Palau, Equatorial Guinea and Mauritius – while Saudi Arabia, the Arab Group and parts of the African Group pushed to keep the item to its usual reporting function.¹⁴

Across interventions, Colombia emphasized the need for a “call to action”; the EU stressed strengthening the Joint Liaison Group (JLG) and coherence across science and implementation; Canada and Australia supported capturing discussions to inform national policy; SIDS highlighted synergies as essential for survival

and effectiveness of the climate regime; and African countries such as Zimbabwe and Nigeria highlighted the importance of a synergies decision at COP30 to support ongoing national resilience efforts.¹⁵

At the end of the first week (SB63), with no consensus to negotiate a full decision, Brazil secured for the SBSTA Chair to prepare a first draft, ensuring that the item would carry forward into the second week. An informal note circulated on 19 November was considered by many of the “champions” mentioned above to be low in ambition, but Parties accepted it due to limited time and the strategic interest, led by Colombia, in ensuring that COP30 delivered at least some outcome on the issue of synergies.

The **draft conclusion**,¹⁶ adopted under Agenda Item 3(a):

- Acknowledges **Party and observer submissions**;
- Recognizes the importance of cooperation and the role of the JLG;
- Invites **further submissions by 1 May 2026** on enhancing coordination among international organizations and the three Rio Convention secretariats, to be considered at SBSTA 64.

In the end, COP30 did not deliver the operational guidance or alignment with recent CBD and UNCCD decisions that many Parties and supporting non-governmental organizations had sought, but it kept the agenda item open and established the first formal entry point for climate-nature synergies within the UNFCCC, creating political momentum to build on ahead of COP31.

Importantly, beyond the agenda item on cooperation with other international organizations, other COP30 negotiated outcomes that reinforced the climate-nature nexus also merit attention: the Mitigation Work Programme and the “Global Mutirão” outcome.

The decision adopted under the Mitigation Work Programme¹⁷ incorporated key elements from the fifth dialogue¹⁸ (19 to 20 May 2025 in Panama City), which took place under the work programme and focused on enabling mitigation solutions in the forest sector, drawing on national and regional experience, and included several notable acknowledgements:

- **The critical role of forests** (boreal, temperate, and tropical forests, as well as mangroves) as carbon stocks and sinks essential for climate resilience, biodiversity, water and food security, livelihoods and sustainable development (paragraph 13(a));
- **Potential synergies** between mitigation, adaptation, biodiversity conservation, land restoration, and sustainable development (paragraph 13(c));
- **Key drivers of deforestation**, including economic pressures on land-use and increasing climate-related risks such as fires, droughts, pests, and extreme temperatures (paragraph 13(d)).

Likewise, the preamble of the COP30 “Global Mutirão” outcome¹⁹ – the political text introduced by the Presidency and adopted as a decision as part of the Belém Package – also included reinforced language on climate-nature integration. It:

- Emphasizes the importance of **conserving, protecting and restoring ecosystems**, including through enhanced efforts to halt and reverse deforestation and forest degradation by 2030, in line with Article 5 of the Paris Agreement.
- Recognizes the need to **address climate change, biodiversity loss, and land and ocean degradation in a comprehensive and synergistic manner**, linked to sustainable development.
- Highlights the **role of terrestrial and marine ecosystems** as sinks and reservoirs of greenhouse gases and underscores the importance of robust social and environmental safeguards.

3. Action Agenda: Translating Synergies into Delivery

The COP30 Action Agenda²⁰ translated climate-nature synergies into delivery primarily through Axis II (*Stewarding Forests, Oceans and Biodiversity*), notably under Objectives 5, 6 and 7, which focus respectively on: (5) investments to halt and reverse deforestation and forest degradation; (6) conserving, protecting and restoring ecosystems with integrated solutions for climate, biodiversity and desertification; and (7) preserving and restoring oceans and coastal ecosystems. Climate-nature synergies were also reflected beyond Axis II, particularly under Axis VI (*Unleashing Enablers and Accelerators*), through Objective 29 on bioeconomy and biotechnology, which positions nature-based industries as enablers of climate and development outcomes.

Across the six axes, the COP30 Action Agenda comprised 30 objectives supported by a total of 123 Plans to Accelerate Solutions (PAS), of which 15 were clustered under Axis II.²¹ The figure that follows presents six plans particularly relevant to climate-nature synergies, including their respective initiatives launched at COP30. Together, these selected PAS illustrate how climate-nature synergies were operationalized through complementary pathways, such as long-term and predictable finance for forests; the scaling of high-integrity jurisdictional approaches to halt deforestation; strengthened institutional and political coherence across the Rio Conventions; and the integration of nature into broader economic and development strategies, including bioeconomy and efforts to tackle environmental crime.

Figure 1 - Climate-Nature Synergies-related Plans to Accelerate Solutions (PAS)

Tropical Forest Forever Facility (TFFF) and Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES)

COP30 marked the official launch of the TFFF, with announced commitments exceeding USD 6.7 billion by the end of the conference,²² in its first phase, with 63 countries endorsing the initiative. The Facility aims to mobilize USD 125 billion in long-term, predictable finance and dedicates at least 20% of payments directly to Indigenous Peoples and Local Communities (IPLCs). A Country Access Platform was also introduced to support eligibility and technical readiness.

Scaling J-REDD+

Through this Plan to Accelerate Solutions, a new Scaling J-REDD+ Coalition²³ was launched at COP30, bringing together governments, Indigenous organizations, investors, and civil society to expand high-integrity jurisdictional REDD+. The initiative seeks to mobilize between USD 3 and 6 billion annually by 2030 to halt and reverse tropical deforestation, building on the Warsaw Framework for REDD+ and the outcomes of the Global Stocktake.

Synergistic implementation across the Rio Conventions

This PAS strengthens integrated implementation across the UNFCCC, CBD and UNCCD by aligning climate, biodiversity and land actions.²⁴ It aims to enhance policy coherence, mobilizes resources, and support the delivery of the Paris Agreement, the Global Biodiversity Framework and Land Degradation Neutrality targets. At COP30, the current

continued on the next page

continuation

and incoming Presidencies of the UNFCCC, CBD, and UNCCD released the *Belém Joint Statement on the Rio Conventions*,²⁵ committing to collaborate in mobilizing non-Party stakeholder actions that synergistically deliver for climate, biodiversity, land and people. As an initiative born from the COP28 Joint Statement on Climate, Nature and People, and as the host initiative of the Rio Synergies PAS, the Synergies Collaboration Platform will play a key role in implementing the declaration's goals in partnership with the Rio Presidencies.

Nature-Based Solutions (NbS) Implementation

More than 1,000 companies and financial institutions are now acting on the Nature Positive for Climate Call to Action, a sixfold increase since COP28.²⁶ NbS implementation continues to expand through science-based targets, disclosure frameworks and investment commitments. The Peatland Breakthrough²⁷ released a global science-based framework aligned with the Paris Agreement and the Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF), including targets to halt the loss of around 430 million hectares of peatlands, restore 30 million hectares by 2030 and ensure sustainable management.

Tackling Environmental Crime to Achieve Zero Deforestation

Hosted by the Global Coalition Against Environmental Crime, whose core partners include Igarapé Institute, The Royal Foundation of The Prince and Princess of Wales (TRF), and the *Alianza Amazónica para la Reducción de los Impactos de la Minería de Oro* (AARIMO), this PAS frames the fight against environmental crime as essential to achieving zero deforestation by 2030.²⁸ It aims to strengthen monitoring and detection, improve legality and traceability in timber and mineral supply chains, and advance regional cooperation across the Amazon Basin and in other tropical forest areas, as well as global cooperation, including under the United Nations Convention against Transnational Organized Crime (UNTOC). By 2028, it seeks to enhance enforcement capacity, expand high-integrity data systems, and consolidate coalitions to disrupt illicit forest economies, contributing directly to GST outcomes, the GBF and the 2030 climate and nature targets.

Bioeconomy to Accelerate NDC Implementation

This PAS²⁹ was launched in a high-level meeting jointly by Brazil, international partners such as the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the Inter-American Development Bank Group (IDB Group), the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), the World Resources Institute (WRI), and NatureFinance. Through the Global Bioeconomy Challenge,³⁰ this three-year initiative seeks to develop common metrics, market frameworks and financing mechanisms to scale a high-integrity global bioeconomy. With a current estimated value of USD 4 trillion (projected to reach USD 30 trillion by 2050), the bioeconomy represents a major frontier for integrating climate mitigation, biodiversity conservation and inclusive territorial development. The initiative provides countries with practical tools to embed bioeconomy strategies into climate plans, reinforcing the Action Agenda's mandate to connect nature-based industries with decarbonization pathways and community-centered development.

4. Mobilization: Expanding Political, Financial, and Societal Support

COP30 generated an unprecedented level of mobilization around integrated climate-nature action, reflecting strong expectations that Belém would deliver meaningful progress on finance, policy coherence, and implementation. A central political signal came from Brazil's President Lula da Silva's call for a "global roadmap to end deforestation" during the Leaders Summit, which gained rapid momentum: by the end of the conference, more than 90 countries, including the EU and over fifty tropical forest nations within the Coalition for Rainforest Nations (CfRN), had formally expressed support.³¹ Leading scientists, including Carlos Nobre, Johan Rockström, Thelma Krug and Paulo Artaxo, issued a joint statement reinforcing that achieving zero deforestation, degradation and fire is indispensable to remain within remaining carbon budgets.³²

Across the Blue Zone, Green Zone and partner spaces, COP30 hosted a wide range of political, scientific and civil society events focused on climate-nature synergies. The COP30 Presidency led two central high-level dialogues: the ministerial roundtable "From Rio to Belém: securing a renewed legacy for climate, biodiversity, land, and sustainable development at COP30,"³³ which gathered more than eight ministers and sixteen Party interventions and significantly strengthened momentum for an outcome under the agenda item on cooperation across conventions; and "Bridging Action Agendas from COP16 to COP30,"³⁴ which brought together the presidencies of the UNFCCC, CBD and UNCCD to align their Action Agendas and identify pathways for integrated implementation.

These discussions were complemented by high-level partner-led initiatives, including "From Talk to Action: Making COP30 a Turning Point for

Synergistic Climate-Nature Action,"³⁵ hosted by the German Federal Ministry for the Environment, Climate Action, Nature Conservation and Nuclear Safety (BMUKN), the Ministry of Environment and Sustainable Development of Colombia, and United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP). The event launched the white paper "From Silos to Synergies,"³⁶ which synthesizes key recommendations from stakeholder dialogues on operationalizing integrated climate-nature action.

Additional non-Party stakeholder-led events further reinforced this momentum, such as "From Trade-offs to Synergies: Aligning Climate and Biodiversity Policies,"³⁷ featuring national and international experts, and senior Party officials such as Brazil's Biodiversity Secretary, Rita Mesquita, and Colombia's lead negotiator, Daniela Durán. Together, these exchanges demonstrated broad political, scientific and societal support for advancing climate-nature synergies, reinforcing Brazil's leadership and consolidating COP30 as a key moment for elevating integrated action across the Rio Conventions.

Finance, philanthropy and private-sector engagement with the climate-nature synergies agenda also accelerated. Beyond the presentation of the "Baku-to-Belém Roadmap to 1.3 Trillion" (see Box below) and the launch of the TFFF, several other initiatives and commitments were announced before and during COP30. For instance, Nature4Climate surveyed 34 investors, who collectively indicated USD 10.4 billion in planned investments in nature-based solutions (NbS) in Brazil through 2027.³⁸ The Emergent Forest Finance Accelerator concluded a USD 23 million transaction with Côte d'Ivoire for forest conservation.³⁹ The Brazil Restoration & Bioeconomy Finance Coalition (BRB FC), led by BTG Pactual, reported USD 5.37 billion mobilized for conservation and restoration across Brazilian biomes, already surpassing half of its USD 10 billion 2030 goal.⁴⁰ The Rockefeller Foundation announced USD 5.4 million to support Brazil's regenerative school meals programme.⁴¹ Meanwhile, the European Union⁴² signed the Belém Call to Action for the Congo Basin Forests,⁴³ renewing its COP26

commitment⁴⁴ to halt and reverse deforestation and forest degradation by 2030 in this region. Likewise, Brazil's National Bank for Economic and Social Development (BNDES) announced BRL 912 million in investments for ecological restoration and silviculture projects involving native species in areas of the Amazon and the Atlantic Forest.⁴⁵

COP30 also stood out for broad whole-of-society mobilization. Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) highlighted that Belém delivered “the most nature-integrated COP to date,” with climate-nature synergies visible across negotiations, pavilions and the Action Agenda.⁴⁶ Indigenous Peoples, Afro-descendant communities, youth and civil society played a prominent role, supported by dedicated spaces such as the People's Summit (*Pavilhão do Círculo dos Povos*, in Portuguese) and the Indigenous peoples-

led *Aldeia COP*, reflecting a strong shift toward implementation rooted in rights, equity, and territorial governance. Climate-nature synergies were also very visible across a range of side events held in the Blue and Green Zones of COP30, as well as across multiple independent venues throughout the city.

Momentum around synergies was further reflected in commitments related to land governance and Indigenous rights. Seventeen governments endorsed the Intergovernmental Land Tenure Commitment, pledging to secure Indigenous land rights on 160 million hectares globally, led by Brazil, Peru and Norway, alongside the Forest & Climate Leaders' Partnership (FCLP) and the Forest Tenure Funders Group.⁴⁷ Brazil also announced the regularization of 63 million hectares of Indigenous and quilombola⁴⁸ territories by 2030.⁴⁹

Baku to Belém Roadmap to 1.3T: Finance as an Enabler of Climate-Nature Synergies⁵⁰

Mandated by the decision on the New Collective Quantified Goal (NCQG) at COP29, the *Baku to Belém Roadmap to 1.3T* was jointly developed by the COP29 and COP30 Presidencies and presented in November 2025 as a reference framework to scale climate finance for developing countries to at least USD 1.3 trillion per year by 2035.⁵¹ The Roadmap, which takes the form of a solutions-oriented report, does not create new mechanisms, but consolidates existing initiatives, leverage points and policy options to accelerate implementation in a coordinated manner.

The Roadmap explicitly recognizes that climate finance increasingly overlaps with nature- and land-related investments, including forests, ecosystems, and agriculture. It highlights the importance of aligning finance with country-driven priorities set out in NDCs and NAPs, as well as strengthening country platforms and integrated planning frameworks to translate climate and development goals into coherent investment strategies.

Across its thematic action fronts, the Roadmap identifies financing nature and supporting ecosystem guardians as core components of the transition, alongside adaptation, mitigation and just transitions. It also points to the potential value of stronger coordination across the Rio Conventions and relevant institutions, including through improved coherence in national planning, investment pipelines and financial instruments capable of delivering co-benefits and greater efficiency in implementation.

By linking the NCQG mandate to country-led implementation and integrated financing pathways, the *Baku to Belém Roadmap* provides an enabling framework for advancing climate-nature synergies as part of broader efforts to align internal and external financial flows with climate-resilient and sustainable development pathways.

5. Looking Forward: Building on the Belém Momentum in 2026

The legacy of Belém lies in the political momentum generated around climate-nature synergies and broader coherence across the three Rio Conventions, even as a gap remains between ambition and outcomes. COP30 demonstrated that integration is politically viable and increasingly demanded. Translating this momentum into durable multilateral governance and implementation, however, will require sustained follow-up beyond the conference cycle.

Looking ahead to 2026, and taking advantage of the three Rio Conventions holding their COPs in 2026, sustained engagement will be required across different actor groups to consolidate and operationalize the advances made in Belém. Parties, civil society and the private sector each have distinct but complementary roles to play. Concrete avenues for engagement include:

- **Supporting the global roadmap to end deforestation**, including through engagement with the Brazilian COP30 Presidency and other key stakeholders, to advance pathways toward zero deforestation in line with climate, biodiversity, and land objectives.
- **Ensuring coherence between the fossil fuel transition roadmap and climate-nature objectives.** This includes preventing mitigation pathways that may appear climate-positive from a carbon perspective but generate trade-offs for nature, territorial integrity, or food systems, such as unsustainable bioenergy expansion.
- **Engagement on the UNFCCC agenda item on cooperation with other international organizations**, including targeted outreach to Parties to support constructive engagement and timely submissions ahead of the 1 May 2026 deadline, building on the procedural opening secured at COP30.
- **Scaling public and private investment in enabling mechanisms**, including nature-based and nature-focused initiatives such as the Tropical Forests Forever Facility (TFFF), Payments for Ecosystem Services (PES), nature credits, and country platforms.
- **Expanding investment in restoration and integrated land-use projects**, including nature-based solutions and community-led initiatives that simultaneously deliver climate mitigation, biodiversity outcomes, and resilience at the territorial level.
- **Maintaining high-level political visibility of Rio synergies**, including through continued engagement by the COP30 Presidency to keep climate-nature integration visible in political spaces, encourage practical follow-up between COPs, and help set the conditions for meaningful, implementation-oriented outcomes in 2026.

Together, these actions can help bridge the gap between political momentum and implementation, ensuring that the advances made in Belém translate into more coherent, high-impact delivery across the Rio Conventions in 2026 and beyond.

Ultimately, in a decade defined by interconnected planetary risks, the ability to deliver integrated climate-nature action is becoming a defining measure of effective multilateralism.⁵² Progress toward global climate goals will depend on the capacity of multilateral processes to overcome silos and translate integrated ambition into action at scale, especially in forest regions that are critical to planetary stability, livelihoods, and development.

End notes

1. This Bulletin was written by Aline Lara, Laura Trajber Waisbich, and Giovanna Kuele of the Igarapé Institute. The authors would like to thank Calder Tsuyuki-Tomlinson for his external review and contributions to an earlier version of the document.
2. The Leaders' Summit provides high-level political direction; negotiations deliver formal decisions under the Convention; the Action Agenda mobilizes non-Party actors and voluntary initiatives to accelerate implementation; and global mobilization broadens political, financial, and societal engagement beyond the negotiating rooms. This four-pillar approach reflects the Global Mutirão framework introduced by the Brazilian COP30 Presidency in its official Letters from the Presidency. COP30 Presidency (2025). [Second Letter from the Presidency](#)
3. Igarapé Institute (2025). [Climate-Nature Synergies: from local to global](#), Strategic Paper 65.
4. CBD COP 16 Decision 16/22, advanced climate–biodiversity synergies by mandating integrated national planning, safeguards and nature-based solutions, and by inviting Parties and stakeholders to submit views on options to enhance policy coherence, including a potential joint work programme across the Rio Conventions; while UNCCD COP16 Decision 8/COP.16, strengthened coherence through joint science–policy work, data interoperability, coordination among national focal points and reinforced collaboration via the Joint Liaison Group. See United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (2024). [Decision adopted by the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity on 1 November 2024](#) and United Nations Convention to Combat Desertification (2024). [Convention Decision 8/COP.16: Promotion and strengthening of relationships with other relevant conventions and international organizations, institutions and agencies](#)
5. Conference of the Parties serving as the meeting of the Parties to the Paris Agreement (CMA) - 2023. [Decision 1/CMA.5: Outcome of the first global stocktake](#)
6. See [Tropical Forest Forever Facility](#) (TFFF)
7. Igarapé Institute (2025). [Climate-Nature Synergies: from local to global](#), Strategic Paper 65.
8. Brazil's Presidency of the Republic (2025). [Speech by President Lula at the Opening of COP30, in Belém \(PA\)](#)
9. The Igarapé Institute advocates for a Global Climate and Nature Council to address the synergies agenda. [Towards a Global Climate and Nature Council: Underpinning the Global Mutirão and Modelling the Future of Governance](#). Global Futures Bulletin, 2025.
10. COP Presidency (2025). [Over USD 5.5 billion Announced for Tropical Forest Forever Facility as 53 Countries Endorse the Historic TFFF Launch Declaration](#)
11. COP30 Presidency (2025). [Call to Action on Integrated Fire Management and Wildfire Resilience](#)
12. COP30 Presidency (2025). [First Letter from the President of COP30, Ambassador André Corrêa do Lago](#)
13. To support this process, Parties and observers were invited to submit views by 30 September 2025 to inform the discussions in November. See: Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice (SBSTA) -2025. [Cooperation with other international organizations](#). This procedural opening built on parallel developments under the Convention on Biological Diversity, where, through decision 16/22 adopted at CBD COP16 in 2024, Parties, observers, and other stakeholders were invited to submit views by 1 May 2025 on options to enhance policy coherence, including a potential joint work programme of the Rio Conventions (See Endnote 4).

14. This Subsidiary Body for Scientific and Technological Advice (SBSTA) item has historically been treated as a procedural stocktake, built around an annual UNFCCC secretariat information note on cooperation with other organizations, often discussed at the mid-year session. Outcomes are typically limited to “taking note/welcoming” the report and inviting further exchanges of views, rather than adopting substantive mandates.
15. This account draws based on direct observation by the Igarapé Institute delegation in formal negotiation sessions, contact groups and Presidency-led consultations during SB62 and COP30.
16. United Nations Convention on Climate Change (2025). [Cooperation with other international organizations](#)
17. United Nations Convention on Climate Change (2025). [Sharm el-Sheikh mitigation ambition and implementation work programme](#)
18. United Nations Convention on Climate Change (2025). [Fifth global dialogue and investment-focused event under the Sharm el-Sheikh mitigation ambition and implementation work programme](#)
19. United Nations Convention on Climate Change (2025). [Global Mutirão: Uniting humanity in a global mobilization against climate change](#)
20. Anchored in the first Global Stocktake (GST), the COP30 Action Agenda translates agreed global goals into concrete action through aligned initiatives, scaled implementation, and enhanced transparency, and is organized around six thematic axes spanning mitigation, adaptation and means of implementation. COP30 Presidency (2025). [Fourth Letter from the Presidency](#)
21. Plans to Accelerate Solutions (PAS) are voluntary, three-year initiatives (2025-2028) under the COP30 Action Agenda designed to mobilize actors, finance and partnerships to accelerate the implementation of agreed outcomes identified through the Global Stocktake. Further details are provided in [COP30 Action Agenda Final Report](#)
22. COP30 Presidency (2025). [COP30 approves Belém Package](#)
23. The Forest & Climate Leader’s Partnership (FCLP). [Countries, Companies, and Civil Society Unite to Launch the Scaling J-REDD+ Coalition at COP30](#)
24. See [Plan to Accelerate Solution: Synergistic implementation across the Rio Conventions](#)
25. See [Belem Joint Statement on the Rio Conventions](#)
26. The [Nature Positive for Climate Action initiative](#) mobilizes companies and financial institutions to integrate nature-positive outcomes into climate strategies, scaling nature-based solutions through science-based targets, disclosure frameworks, and increased investment aligned with the Paris Agreement and the Global Biodiversity Framework.
27. The [Peatland Breakthrough](#) is an initiative that mobilizes finance and partnerships to protect, restore and sustainably manage peatlands, guided by science-based global targets for 2030 and beyond.
28. See [Plan to Accelerate Solution: Tackling Environmental Crime to Achieve Zero Deforestation](#)
29. See [Plan to Accelerate Solution: Bioeconomy](#)
30. See [Global Bioeconomy Challenge](#)
31. World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF) - 2025. [Small wins leave gaps at COP30; core climate goals stay out of reach](#)
32. Planetary Science Pavilion (2025). [Scientists statement on state of COP30 Negotiations, November 19, 2025](#)
33. International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) - 2025. [IUCN calls for stronger collaboration among Rio Conventions at COP30 in Belém](#)
34. United Nations Climate Change (2025). [Bridging Action Agendas from COP16 to COP30: Strengthening](#)

[Synergies Across Land, Climate, and Nature](#)

35. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) - 2025. [From Talk to Action: Making COP30 a Turning Point for Synergistic Climate-Nature Action](#)
36. United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) - 2025. [From Silos to Synergies](#)
37. Earth Negotiations Bulletin (2025). [From Trade-offs to Synergies: Aligning Climate and Biodiversity Policies](#)
38. See the [Nature4Climate](#) YouTube video about COP30.
39. Emergent (2025). [Côte d'Ivoire Signs Landmark \\$23 Million Deal for Verified Emissions Reductions with Emergent](#)
40. Businesswire (2025). [Brazil Coalition for Restoration and Bioeconomy Financing Accelerates Capital Mobilization](#)
41. The Rockefeller Foundations (2025). [Rockefeller Foundation Supports Brazil-Led Food Solutions To Nourish People at COP30](#)
42. European Commission (2025). [EU secures an agreement on a global response to keep the 1.5C limit within reach](#), press release.
43. French government - Elysée (2025). [Belém Call to Action for the Congo Basin Forests](#). Press release.
44. European Commission (2021). [COP26: European Commission announces €1 billion pledge to protect world forests](#)
45. CapitalReset (2025). [BNDES aprova R\\$ 912 milhões do Fundo Clima para empresas de reflorestamento](#)
46. Langston, R. (2025). [I've never seen such a nature-integrated COP," says CDP](#), Environmental Finance.
47. Hanbury, S. (2025). [Governments commit to recognizing 160 million hectares of Indigenous land'](#), Mongabay.
48. Quilombola communities are legally recognized Afro-Brazilian traditional communities descended from enslaved Africans who formed quilombos, or resistance settlements, during the colonial period.
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The Igarapé Institute is an independent think-and-do tank that conducts research, develops solutions, and establishes partnerships to influence public and corporate policies and practices, addressing key challenges related to nature, climate, and security in Brazil and worldwide. Igarapé is a nonprofit, nonpartisan organization based in Rio de Janeiro, operating at both local and global levels.

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